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Research Article

**RESTING ECG CHANGES IN PATIENTS OF ISCHEMIC
HEART-STROKE**Dr Amir Farooq Khan¹, Dr Fiza Batool Kazmi², Dr Rida Maria²¹ Khyber Medical College, Peshawar, ² Foundation University Medical College, Islamabad.**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Electrocardiography transmits information about the electrical function of the heart by changing the state of its component waves, namely the P, QRS and T waves, which represent one cycle of the heart. The amplitude and interval of the P-QRS-T segment determine the function of the heart. Cardiac arrhythmia manifests itself as a state of abnormal electrical activity in the heart, which is a hazard to humans. Currently, the onset of ischemic cerebrovascular disease is associated with electrocardiographic changes in patients who did not have primary heart disease.

Aim: We estimated the frequency of electrocardiographic changes to be remarkable. The aim of the study is to analyze heart disease in electrocardiogram (ECG) signals for cardiac arrhythmias that lead to ischemic stroke, using the result of normal and abnormal ECG waves.

Methods: Study sample of 75 patients which had been admitted to the Cardiology department of PIMS Hospital Islamabad for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. A 12-lead resting ECG was performed on all patients, using Cardiofax S ECG-1250K for high-level 12-lead analysis. All records were translated by a similar person who is a cardiologist who did not know the medical history of the subject. In particular, the following ECG abnormalities were looked for: ST segment elevation or depression, T wave aberration (inversion or high T wave), bundle branch block, left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH), arrhythmia, QT wave lengthening, and other changes.

In the results of 75 patients, approximately (58.67%) were men, and (41.33%) women, their mean age (62 years). The control group consisted of (52%) men and (48%) women, mean age (61.5 years). The frequency of electrocardiographic changes in the study group was (58.67%), while in the control group - the patient (25.33%).

Key words: Arrhythmia, Cardiac ischemia, Resting ECG, Ischemic Stroke, ST Segment depression.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Amir Farooq Khan,**

Khyber Medical College, Peshawar.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Cardiovascular disease is the leading source of death worldwide and has an impact on financial health. The high morbidity and mortality associated with these diseases make the diagnosis and treatment of these diseases the primary clinical practice¹⁻². Electrocardiograms are important tests for assessing cardiovascular disease; earlier recognition of the prevalence of abnormalities in the studied population is valuable for the interpretation of ECG results³⁻⁴. In addition, ECG abnormalities are autonomously associated with the presence of coronary heart disease and poor outcome in this disease. The prevalence of electrocardiographic abnormalities changes with age and gender. Recently, numerous studies have focused on the unique aspects of heart disease in women to improve its detection and treatment. In general, an electrocardiogram (EKG) is used to monitor heart rhythm. The resting ECG is the most commonly used diagnostic test for the cardiovascular system⁵⁻⁶. About 75 million are exhibited each year in the United States alone and probably twice worldwide. ECG changes appear early in the course of cardiovascular disease and typically include changes such as sinus tachycardia, QTc prolongation, QT dispersion, changes in heart rate variability, changes in the ST-T segment, and left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) ⁷⁻⁸. These and other progressions, identified using a resting ECG, often together with a functional ECG, are used to identify silent ischemia, assess prognosis, and predict future risk. Since the ECG is non-invasive and is generally simple to perform, it is used as part of the test system conducted as part of the annual clinical evaluation of the symptomatic population worldwide⁹. Dogan et al. Reported that the ECG abnormalities in ischemic stroke occur in approximately 65% of all patients without primary heart disease. The aim of the study is to demonstrate that electrocardiographic changes in ischemic heart stroke without primary heart disease require reconsideration of heart disease.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

A 12-lead resting ECG was performed on all patients, using Cardiofax S ECG-1250K for high-level 12-lead analysis. All records were translated by a similar person who is a cardiologist who did not know the medical history of the subject. In particular, the following ECG abnormalities were looked for: ST segment elevation or depression, T wave aberration (inversion or high T wave), His bundle branch block, left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH), arrhythmia, QT wave lengthening, and other changes. Study sample of 75 patients which had been admitted to the Cardiology department of PIMS Hospital Islamabad for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. Stroke according to the criteria of the World Health Organization as a rapidly developing symptom of global or focal brain dysfunction. The diagnosis and subtype of stroke were confirmed by computed tomography of the brain.

Admission Criteria

- Cerebrovascular disease.
- Admission in the first 24 hours of the event.
- Electrocardiogram taken within 24 hours of admission.
- Patient age 45 and older.

Exclusion Criteria

- Previous history of heart disease.
- Hemorrhagic stroke or head injury.
- Liver, kidneys and metabolic disorders.
- Age less than 45 years old.
- Basal artery failure.
- Onset of stroke lasting more than 24 hours

The study sample included 75 age-free stroke patients who were admitted within the above-mentioned period.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The patient group and the control group are divided by gender, with approximately 41.33% of the patients being female and 58.67% of the male patients with a mean age of 62 years, while the control group was female 48% and men approximately 52% were male. 61.5 years as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Gender wise distribution of study group and control group

Gender	Study Group		Control Group	
	n	%	n	%
Male	44	58.67%	39	52.00%
Female	31	41.33%	36	48.00%
Total	75	100.00%	75	100.00%

The frequency of ECG changes in the study group with ECG abnormalities was observed in 44 patients

(58.67%), while 19 of the 75 control patients had ECG abnormalities as shown in Table 2. Table 3

shows the frequency of changes in electrocardiography both in the study group and in the control group: T inversion is more frequent, followed by ST segment depression in patients in the study group, while in the control group it was lower with T inversion by about 16% and ST reduction around 1.33%. A normally functioning heart is controlled by the central nervous system. The central

nervous system manages heart rate, vasomotor tone, blood pressure, and cardiac output. Arrhythmia changes the rhythm of ischemic stroke by 51%, and its result is consistent with our study. Reporting the frequency of new electrocardiographic changes in ischemic heart stroke (15-30%), and their result is relatively lower than the result of our study group.

Table 2 Electrocardiographic findings among study group and control group

ECG	Study Group		Control Group	
	n	%	n	%
Abnormal	44	58.67%	19	25.33%
Normal	31	41.33%	56	74.67%
Total	75	100.00%	75	100.00%

Cardiac arrhythmia is common (51%) than ischemic stroke, and this result is consistent with our research. Generally, the electrocardiographic changes are T inversion followed by ST segment depression as an indication of ischemia that is most often identified

with catecholamine release. This difference in electrocardiographic changes is due to the definitions and criteria on which we rely. These changes are of significant value in reconsidering heart disease.

Table 3 The frequency of ECG changes among study group and control group

ECG Changes	Study Group		Control Group	
	n	%	n	%
MI – Pathological Q wave with or without ST and T changes	8	10.67%	1	1.33%
IHD - without Q waves	1	1.33%	0	-
Atrial fibrillation	4	5.33%	0	-
Left ventricular hypertrophy	3	4.00%	1	1.33%
T wave inversion	14	18.67%	12	16.00%
ST segment depression	9	12.00%	1	1.33%
ST elevation	5	6.67%	4	5.33%
Total	44	58.67%	19	25.33%

Criteria for the definition of changes in the electrocardiograph trace

- 12-lead ECG with standardized (10 mm / mv) velocity (25 mm / s).
- ST segment depression: oblique or flat depression (1 mm), raise (1 mm). Chest lead elevation (v1, v2 2 mm) significant.
- Q wave assessed in lead (1, 2, AVF).
- T wave normally upright normal decrease less than (0.1mm) abnormal.
- U wave characterized as negative with a progressive wave (0.1 mv of positive u wave depth when it is higher than 25% R).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

It can be concluded that the correlations of age and gender with the electrocardiographic abnormalities found in this study can help improve predictive ECG assessment and contribute to the diagnosis and therefore surveillance of many regular cardiovascular diseases in primary care. Electrocardiographic abnormalities are common in early-onset ischemic stroke patients despite normally functioning heart, transcendentally as T inversion followed by ST segment depression, and these changes are significant for these patients¹¹. Cardiac abnormalities, including coronary blood flow disorders, may play a role in the causes of ischemic stroke and are essential as prognostic measures. We observed that other ECG changes comprising pathologic Q-wave, ST-segment depression, ST-segment elevation, and prominent-U

wave may also occur in selected or non-selected stroke patients, thereby simulating an acute myocardial injury. The high frequency of ECG abnormalities in our study population is in line with the frequency reported in the literature. According to the results of these studies, the ischemia-like ECG abnormalities and QT interval prolongation can occur in more than 90% of the patients with ischemic or hemorrhagic stroke, and this rate will decrease by 8–40% if patients with a history of known heart disease and treatment by cardiac drugs are excluded¹². In an early study of 150 patients with acute stroke, Golstein detected QT prolongation in 45%, ischemic changes in 39%, arrhythmias in 27%, and U-waves in 28% of their patients. In a study on patients with ischemic stroke but without history of primary heart disease, Dogan *et al* found ischemia-like ECG changes in 65% of patients, QTc interval prolongation in 26%, and arrhythmias in 44% of them. In the study of Lindgren *et al*. transient ST-T changes were found in 54% of patients with ischemic stroke with no primary heart disease. Prominent U-wave, QT interval prolongation, and arrhythmia were observed in 17%, 13%, and 4% of them, respectively. Compared with our study, however, that study included only 24 patients with cerebral infarction¹³⁻¹⁴. On the other hand, in the study of McDermott *et al* ST-segment depression was noted in only 8% of the selected patients without a history of coronary heart disease, whereas it was observed in 60% of the patients. Most of the ECG abnormalities described after an acute cerebral event were linked to SAH. In SAH, the incidence of ECG abnormalities ranges from 49% to 100%, including changes in ST segment (15% to 51% of patients), T-waves (12% to 92%), prominent U-waves (4% to 47%), QT prolongation (11% to 66%), pathological Q waves, and sinus dysrhythmias. Attempts to correlate the ECG abnormalities with the location of the brain lesion have been made previously by several authors, but the reported results are divergent. The direct stimulation of many areas of the CNS is known to result in abnormal ECG patterns; while no relationship of the ECG changes, to the site of the bleeding aneurysm, was found by Cropp and Manning, Shuster and Hunt *et al*. In studies focused on the intracranial vascular spasm after SAH and the appearance of ECG abnormalities, Wilkins *et al* showed no relationship, while Stober and Kunze were able to find a correlation between cerebral arteries spasms of the left hemisphere, T-wave inversion, and QT prolongation¹⁵. A correlation between arrhythmias and T-wave abnormalities and hemorrhages in the anterior cerebral circulation has been reported in patients with cerebral hemorrhages. Dogan *et al* observed that lesion of insular cortex, which lies beneath frontoparietal and superior

temporal opercula, leads to several cardiac abnormalities such as ischemic ECG changes, arrhythmias, and myocytolysis.

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